

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF VOCATIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Xudoyberdiyeva Gulchexra Isamidinovna

doctoral student, Chirchik State

Pedagogical Institute, Tashkent region

E-mail: xudoyberdiyeva.gulchexra.1988@mail.ru

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Annotation. One of the important tasks of our research is the analysis of the model curriculum, curricula, materials, manuals, literature used in the teaching of English to students of non-philological disciplines (history, chemistry, etc.). The main purpose of this is to study the practical role of the problem of professional approach in improving the effectiveness of teaching English to higher education students.

Keywords: Pedagogy, subject, procedural, skill, qualification, terminology

In the process of teaching English, communication, texts and language tools, which include the basis of the language being taught, enter into these situations. Speaking skills and competences are understood as a procedural aspect in teaching a foreign language.

It is important to have professional knowledge and skills about different methods of pedagogy in vocational guidance teaching in English. J. Jalolov, one of the scientists who conducted extensive research in this field in our country, takes a deep approach to foreign language teaching methods in his scientific research and explains in detail the specific features, advantages and disadvantages of the methods, their goals and tasks.

In his research, the scientist distinguishes three types of methodological methods: Grammatical and Mant-translation.

A.A. Verbitsky, V.V. Safonova, I.I. In Khaleeva's analysis, the relationship between professional vocabulary and terminology in the field of teaching professional literature and professional literature was revealed in scientific research.

Professional English language training in scientific researches and non-philological universities is aimed at the ability of specialists to apply linguistic competence and knowledge in practice during their future activities, to form an active and creative person.

The next part of the sample subject program includes the following components: an introduction to the subject, goals and objectives, a planned list of topics for practical training, a list of topics and recommended topics for students' independent work, literature. According to the thematic plan, the goals and tasks of this subject belong to the direction of higher education. Among the students

who have mastered the basic education program, to increase the level of knowledge of a foreign language and to acquire the necessary competencies for solving problems, and the observed goal of teaching in the English language textbook published for non-philological faculties is to analyze texts from scientific literature, communication skills of students of the non-philological faculty suitable for their future professions. It is emphasized that it should be formed. Therefore, professional problems in a foreign language, as well as the use of key professional oral speech, will have a good effect.

- independent improvement of students in teaching English for professional purposes.

- development of skills and competencies in the field of oral and written speech, which are important in order to participate in international communication in professional and academic activities. Since speaking is more important than writing, it is better to use speaking to develop writing.

- preparing students for independent improvement in teaching English for professional purposes.

the goals and tasks of the course aimed at developing the professional and communicative competence of future specialists are not properly formed as a linguistic science.

The reason for this is that the author of this sample curriculum did not work with specialists in history, chemistry, and biology with a professional approach, that is, he had (English-language) linguistic training, but he did not have a professional approach.

English textbooks for students should be published by the authors E.I. Serebrennikova and I.Y. Kruglyakolla, in cooperation with professors of the institute specialized in chemistry and other sciences, with excellent knowledge of foreign language specialists. That is, the intended goal of foreign language vocational training is defined as formation of reading skills suitable for reading and understanding English texts and formation of oral speech skills and competencies based on the language materials presented in the curriculum.

After the goals and objectives of the modern course, the essence of science and the list of topics for practical training are given.

We may determine that it is not appropriate for the subject matter in the program. By expanding the topic, the author assigns specific topics to students for independent work. Based on the comparative analysis, it was found that it does not match the topic.

For example, in the English language manual published by K.L. Bliznicheko, N.M. Press for students of chemical engineering faculties, the main focus is on students' reading and understanding of scientific and technical texts.

With the help of the given exercises, it is also tasked to restore the basis of grammar, to form words, to strengthen the active lexical units being studied, the information in this guide helps to improve students' written speech [61;-b;119-131.]

In our opinion, the content of the subject, for practical training and independent work, should be oriented and simplified to the profession using the above-mentioned manuals and literature, because we believe that it is only theoretical, but not professionally approached, and in addition, the sample program is not formed according to the level of professional and students.

- The non-philological university aims to achieve the above goals by working with a modular curriculum. These goals and objectives include:

- It is necessary to implement democratic principles during studies in higher education and expand academic freedom and opportunities for higher education institutions.

- In the process of scientific research in higher education institutions, it made it possible to meet the changing needs of society and achieve high scientific thinking achievements.

- Working in cooperation with international countries, he implemented the level of skill exchange and training of specialists based on this situation.

- It is necessary to form model, literature, materials specific to the lexical and grammatical knowledge of a foreign language, which is important for the fulfillment of communicative goals, and to obtain the national level.

- In order to achieve a professional level of foreign language in the course of the lesson, with a professional approach, to write household information and messages, dialogues, stories, essays appropriate to the topics, to know and design technologies in the use of information systems, to read documents related to work, to understand what they have read, to get information and to use them to have the skills to be able to give oral speech, to be able to translate terms and texts related to the profession.

- Applying innovation methods by professionally directing students to the skills of theoretical and practical speech, discussion of scientific debates while studying English.

-Relying on the opinion of N. A. Svich, D. D. Djantasova among the most important aspects of the teaching content, he envisages a new approach to the

formation of the content of foreign language teaching in a non-philological university with professional orientation. These situations greatly affect the professional activities of students.

- It is known that professional development, knowledge of the English language in most cases is aimed at achievements in scientific fields, therefore, when talking about the content of teaching a foreign language in non-philological directions, it is known from the research of N.D. Galskova that it has two aspects: subject and mentioned procedural aspects [94; 336-b].

As a summary, in the detailed bibliography, there is almost 1 textbook in English published in the USA in 2012 from 35 sources, there are no comparable textbooks in other foreign languages.

In this case, great attention should be paid to teaching English as a means of communication with social and professional applications.

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